

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH SCIENCE & MANAGEMENT

EXACT SOLUTIONS OF A CLASS OF NONLINEAR PARTIAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS $u_{xt}=u^{2n+1}$ WHERE n IS NON ZERO REAL RATIONAL NUMBER

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Keywords: Solutions, Nonlinear , Partial Differential Equations, Real, Rational number, Non zero, Lie Group, Similarity Transformation, Generators, Lie Algebra

Abstract

Using Lie Group Similarity Transformation, a class of nonlinear partial differential equations, $u_{xt} = u^{2n+1}$ where n is any real rational number of the form p/q where p and q are any positive or negative integers ,except $n = 0$ and $n = -1/2$ is reduced to second order nonlinear ordinary differential equation and found exact solutions . Each and every exact solution is a combination of a pair of exact distinct solutions and both exist independently. They form a new class of solutions of Klein-Gordon family of nonlinear partial differential equations.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7810573

Introduction

CS The nonlinear partial differential equation (NPDE),

$$u_{xt} = F(u) \quad (1.01)$$

where $F(u)$ is either polynomial in u or trigonometric functions are well known in Theoretical Physics as Klein-Gordon equations. When

$$F(u) = \sin u \quad (1.02)$$

is the well known Sine-Gordon equation, first introduced by Backlund [01] in 1876 as a model of nonlinear pseudo spherical surface with constant negative curvature in differential geometry. Backlund introduced a new method of solving NPDEs , that later called as Auto Backlund Transformation (ABT) and found exact solution of (1.01) and (1.02) . ABT is a special case of contact transformation [02] by which one can transform a class of NPDEs of second order to a pair of first order NPDEs .

Lie Group Similarity Transformation (LGST) is also a special case of contact transformation [02] based on symmetry of a NPDE. If the given second order NPDE in two independent variables is invariant under an infinitesimal point group transformation [02, 03] ,then one can find the possible symmetries of that NPDE . Corresponding to each symmetry one can reduce that two independent variables NPDE to a NODE of second order, so that all exact solutions of that NODE also will be the exact solutions of given NPDE.

In this study, the method of LGST is using to reduce the (1.01) when

$$F(u) = u^{2n+1}, \quad (1.03)$$

where n is any real rational number of the form $\frac{p}{q}$, both positive and negative integers ,other than $n = 0$ and $n = -\frac{1}{2}$, into a second order NODE and found exact solutions for all values above n , Each of those exact solutions

is combination of two distinct exact solutions, that are invariant under respective symmetries.

LIE GROUP SIMILARITY TRANSFORMATIONS METHOD FOR NONLINEAR PARTIAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION

Essential details of the Lie continuous point group similarity transformation method [03] to reduce the number of independent variables of a nonlinear partial differential equation (NPDE) so as to obtain respective ordinary differential equation (ODE) [04] is the following. Let the given NPDE in two independent variables x and t and one dependent variable u be

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$$F(x, t, u, u_t, u_x, u_{tt}, u_{xx}, \dots) = 0, \tag{2.01}$$

where $u_t, u_x \dots$ are all partial derivatives of dependent variables $u(x, t)$ with respect to the independent variable t and x respectively.

When we apply a family of one parameter infinitesimal continuous point Lie group transformations,

$$x = x + \epsilon X(x, t, u) + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.02}$$

$$t = t + \epsilon T(x, t, u) + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.03}$$

$$u = u + \epsilon U(x, t, u) + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.04}$$

then we get the infinitesimals of the variables u, t and x as U, T, X respectively and ϵ is an infinitesimal parameter. The derivatives of u are also transformed as

$$u_x = u_x + \epsilon[U_x] + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.05}$$

$$u_{xx} = u_{xx} + \epsilon[U_{xx}] + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.06}$$

$$u_{tt} = u_{tt} + \epsilon[U_{tt}] + O(\epsilon^2), \tag{2.07}$$

where $[U_x], [U_{xx}], [U_{tt}]$ are the infinitesimals of the derivatives u_x, u_{xx}, u_{tt} respectively. These are called first and second extensions and that are given by [03],

$$[U_x] = U_x + (U|u - X_x)u_x - X_u u_x^2 - T_x u_t - T_x u_x u_t, \tag{2.08}$$

$$[U_{xx}] = U_{xx} + (2U_{xu} - X_{xx})u_x + (U|uu - 2X_{xu})u_x^2 - X_{uu}u_x^3 + (U_u - 2X_x u_{xx} - 3X_u u_x u_{xx} - T_{xx}u_t - 2T_{xu}u_x u_t - T_{uu}u_x^2 u_t - 2T_x u_{xt} - T_u u_{xx} u_t - 2T_u u_{xt} u_x), \tag{2.09}$$

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$$[U_{tt}] = U_{tt} + [2U_{tu} - T_{tt}]u_t - X_{tt}u_x + [U_{uu} - 2T_{uu}]u_t^2 - 2X_{tu}u_x u_t - T_{uu}u_t^3 - X_{uu}u_t^2 u_x + [U_u - 2T_t]u_{tt} - 2X_t u_{xt} - X_u u_{tt} u_t - X_u u_{tt} u_x - 3X_u u_{xt} u_t, \tag{2.10}$$

$$[U_{xt}] = U_{xt} + (U_{xu} - T_{xt})u_t + (U_{tu} - X_{xt})u_x + (U_u - X_x - T_t)u_{xt} - T_x u_{tt} - X_t u_{xx} + (U_{uu} - X_{xu} - T_{tu})u_x u_t - T_{xu}u_t^2 - X_{tu}u_x u_x - 2X_u u_x u_{xt} - X_u u_t u_{xt} - 2T_u u_t u_{xt} - T_u u_x u_{tt} - X_{uu}u_t u_x^2 - T_{uu}u_t^2 u_x, \tag{2.11}$$

The invariant transformation requirements of given NPDE (2.01) under the set of above transformations lead to the invariant surface conditions,

$$T \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} + X \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} + U \frac{\partial F}{\partial u} + [U_x] \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_x} + [U_{tt}] \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_{tt}} + [U_{xx}] \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_{xx}} + [U_{xt}] \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_{xt}} = 0. \tag{2.12}$$

On solving above invariant surface condition (2.12), the infinitesimals X, T, U can be uniquely obtained, that give the similarity groups under which the given NPDE (2.01) is invariant. This gives

$$T \frac{du}{dt} + X \frac{du}{dx} - \frac{du}{dU} = 0, \tag{2.13}$$

The solutions of (2.13) are obtained by Lagrange's condition,

$$\frac{dt}{T} = \frac{dx}{X} = \frac{du}{U}. \tag{2.14}$$

This yields,

$$x = x(t, C_1, C_2) \tag{2.15}$$

and

$$u = u(t, C_1, C_2) \tag{2.16}$$

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where C_1 and C_2 are arbitrary integration constants and the constant C_1 plays the role of an independent variable called the similarity variable s and C_2 that of a dependent variable called the similarity solution $u(s)$ such that exact solution of given NPDE (2.01) becomes

$$u(x, t) = u(s) . \tag{2.17}$$

On substituting (2.17) in given NPDE (2.01) that reduced to an ordinary differential equation (ODE) with s as independent variable and $u(s)$ as dependent variable. Then all solutions $u(s)$ of this reduced ODE also solutions of given PDE (2.01) through (2.17) .

LIE GROUP SIMILARITY TRANSFORMATION OF GIVEN NPDE

Let the given NPDE (1.01) and (1.03) be

$$u_{xt} = u^{2n+1} . \tag{3.01}$$

Then the invariant surface condition (2.11) of (3.01) gives

$$[U_{xt}] = (2n+1) u^{2n} U, \tag{3.02}$$

where $[U_{xt}]$ is the second extensions of u_{xt} . Then substitute the expansions $[U_{xt}]$ from (2.11) in (3.02) and equate the coefficients of u and its derivatives as zero, we get the following constraint equations .

$$\begin{aligned} U_{xt} - (2n+1) u^{2n} U &= 0 , \\ U_{xu} - T_{xt} &= 0 , \\ U_u - X_x - T_t &= 0 , \\ U_{uu} - X_{xu} - T_{ut} &= 0 , \\ T_x = 0 , X_t = 0 , X_u = 0 , T_u &= 0 . \end{aligned} \tag{3.04}$$

On solving above constrained equations , we get

$$X = Cx + v \tag{3.05}$$

$$T = - C t + k , \tag{3.06}$$

and

$$U = 0. \tag{3.07}$$

The Lagrange's conditions (2.14) gives

$$\frac{dx}{X} = \frac{dt}{T} = \frac{du}{U} \tag{3.08}$$

leads to the following similarity variable $s(x, t)$

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$$s(x, t) = [-C^2xt + C(kx - vt) + (kv)]. \tag{3.09}$$

Where C , k and v are arbitrary integration constants . So the similarity solution of (3.01) as

$$u(x, t) = u(s) . \tag{3.10}$$

Substitute (3.10) in (3.01) we get the similarity reduced ODE equation of (3.01) as

$$s \frac{d^2u}{ds^2} + \frac{du}{ds} = - \frac{1}{C^2} u^{2n+1}. \tag{3.11}$$

The exact solution of above ODE (3.11) is

$$u(s) = s^{-1/2n} \tag{3.12}$$

From (3.09), (3.10) and (3.12), we get the exact solution of the given NPDE (3.01) as

$$u(x, t) = [-C^2(x^2 - t^2) + C(kx - vt) + kv]^{-1/2n} \tag{3.13}$$

where

$$C^2 = -\frac{4n^2}{(2n+1)} \tag{3.14}$$

Above exact solution (3.13) of the given NPDE (3.01) is valid all values n , except $n=0$ and $n = -\frac{1}{2}$. Also, for above values n can be both negative as well as positive real rational numbers of the form $\frac{p}{q}$, where p and q are any nonzero integers, except $p=0$ and $\frac{p}{q} = \frac{1}{2}$.

DISCUSSION

The exact solution (3.13) of the given NPDE (3.01) has two sub solutions when the arbitrary integration constants k and v take the values zero and nonzero. When

$k = v = 0$, we get first type of exact solution and the second type of exact solution is possible when $k \neq 0$ and $v \neq 0$. Even then, exclusive travelling wave type solution with $(kx - vt)$ alone is not possible due to the constant coefficient C can not be zero. So each and every allowed values n of (3.14), we get two distinct types of exact solutions and

Known, NPDE (3.01) of the type of Klein – Gordon (KG) family of equations having exact solutions exclusively depending on the travelling wave type term $(kx - vt)$, but in the above study we found that such type solutions are not possible. As such, above solutions are belonging to a new class of exact solutions of KG family of equations. This author already reported this new types of solutions to other members of KG family of equations [04,05,06,07].

Corresponding to the infinitesimals (3.05), (3.06) and (3.07), we get three Lie Group generators [03] as follows,

$$G_1 = x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - t \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tag{4.01}$$

$$G_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tag{4.02}$$

and

$$G_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tag{4.03}$$

These generators form following Lie algebras [03] as

$$[G_1, G_2] = -G_2 \tag{4.04}$$

$$[G_1, G_3] = G_3 \tag{4.05}$$

and

$$[G_2, G_3] = 0 \tag{4.06}$$

LGST method is a powerful method solving nonlinear partial differential equations, provided the given NPDE is invariant under that transformation and the resultant reduced differential is able to solve exactly. This author used this method even for coupled NPDE [08] and found exact solutions.

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